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Monthly Report November 2025

SENTINEL Wild Birds

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SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. The data in this report are based on previously unpublished samples from seven nodes, collected from September 2025 to November 2025, together with some backlogged samples from July and August 2025 (all from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea).

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report was published on 5th of November 2025 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17533839>), and as of 15th November 2025, test results have been submitted for 2,332 samples taken from 1,561 individuals representing 28 taxa from seven nodes in and near Europe (Table 1). Of the 2,332 collected samples, 953 (41%) were cloacal swabs, 938 (40%) tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 365 (16%) fecal samples, 30 (1%) combined swabs (choana + cloacal), 30 (1%) feather samples, 15 (<1%) pooled organs, and 1 (<1%) brain sample.

HPAI detection

Of all samples, 137 (6%) tested positive for avian influenza virus. One sample, from a Eurasian Teal from Italy, contained highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI; H5N1) virus (Figure 1; Table 2).

Other subtypes

Subtyped rRT-PCR-positive samples from Latvia included five H6N2 viruses (from four Mallards and one Eurasian Wigeon), three H1N2 viruses (from two Mallards and one from a Northern Shoveler), one H1N5, one H3N8, and one sample positive for H12 together with H8 and N4 (all from Mallards). One additional H13 virus with undetermined NA subtype was also detected in a Mallard from Latvia.

In Sweden, four Mallard samples were positive for H5 by rRT-PCR, but their NA subtypes are pending confirmation by whole genome sequencing.

Prevalence and host species sampled

The most sampled species were Barnacle Goose (468 individuals), Eurasian Teal (454 individuals), and Mallard (445 individuals; Table 1). High bird-level prevalence in species with a sample size of at least 40 individuals was found in Mallard (12%), Eurasian Teal (7%), and Great Cormorant (2%; Table 1). Notably high prevalence was also found in Sandwich Tern (5 of 13 individuals; 38%). Overall bird-level prevalence was 6% (96 of 1561 individuals; Table 1).

TABLE 1 Most recently sampled individuals in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of individuals sampled in the wild, number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza virus as well as bird-level prevalence. The table includes previously unpublished samples from July to November 2025.

Group/species	Node 1 Estonia		Node 2 Latvia		Node 2 Sweden		Node 4 Georgia		Node 6 Austria		Node 6 Switzerland		Node 7 Italy		Node 8 France		Node 9 Spain		Total		
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Prev.
<i>Waterfowl</i>																					
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0%
Bean Goose	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0%
Barnacle Goose	224	0	0	0	244	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	468	0	0%
Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3	0	0%
Mallard	3	0	49	17	329	35	38	1	5	0	4	0	3	1	2	0	12	0	445	54	12%
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0%
Northern Shoveler	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	33%
Eurasian Wigeon	0	0	4	1	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	9	1	11%
Marbled Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0%
Eurasian Teal	0	0	0	0	8	3	383	23	0	0	0	0	27	2	36	5	0	0	454	33	7%
Garganey	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0%
Common Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Red-crested Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	6	0	0%
Ferruginous Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	0	16	0	0%
<i>Cormorants</i>																					
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	8	0	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	1	2%
<i>Hérons</i>																					
Black-crowned Night Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3	0	0%
Little Egret	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3	0	0%
Grey Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Purple Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0%
<i>Storks, Ibises et al.</i>																					
Eurasian Spoonbill	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0%
<i>Rails</i>																					
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	5	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	40	0	48	0	0%
<i>Waders</i>																					
Purple Sandpiper	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Dunlin	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Common Sandpiper	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Common Redshank	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	100%
<i>Larids</i>																					
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	6	5	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	5	38%
Sandwich Tern	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
<i>Others</i>																					
Unknown Species	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Total	239	0	56	19	599	45	438	24	26	0	47	0	31	3	38	5	87	0	1561	96	6%

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FIGURE 1 Sample sites in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Sample sites for the 1,561 individuals sampled in Estonia, Latvia, Sweden, Georgia, Austria, Switzerland, Italy, France, and Spain. The figure includes previously unpublished samples from July to November 2025.

TABLE 2 Most recently collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus. The table includes previously unpublished samples from July to November 2025.

Group/species	Node 1 Estonia			Node 2 Latvia			Node 2 Sweden			Node 4 Georgia			Node 6 Austria			Node 6 Switzerland			Node 7 Italy			Node 8 France			Node 9 Spain			Total		
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI			
<i>Waterfowl</i>																														
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
Bean Goose	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0
Barnacle Goose	224	0	0	0	0	0	245	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	469	0	0
Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Mallard	3	0	0	49	17	0	469	61	0	76	1	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	9	1	0	4	0	0	24	0	0	643	80	0
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0
Northern Shoveler	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	0
Eurasian Wigeon	0	0	0	4	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	11	1	0
Marbled Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0
Eurasian Teal	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	3	0	765	37	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	81	2	1	72	5	0	0	0	0	929	47	1
Garganey	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22	0	0
Common Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
Red-crested Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	10	0	0
Ferruginous Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	0	0	32	0	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																														
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	2	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45	2	0
<i>Hérons</i>																														
Black-crowned Night Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	6	0	0
Little Egret	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	6	0	0
Grey Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Purple Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	4	0	0
<i>Storks, Ibises et al.</i>																														
Eurasian Spoonbill	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																														
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	80	0	0	90	0	0
<i>Waders</i>																														
Purple Sandpiper	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Dunlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Common Sandpiper	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Common Redshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
<i>Larids</i>																														
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	5	0
Sandwich Tern	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Others</i>																														
Unknown Species	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Total	239	0	0	56	19	0	746	72	0	875	38	0	26	0	0	47	0	0	93	3	1	76	5	0	174	0	0	2332	137	1

A weekly compilation of all 20,834 samples (positive and negative; including previously published), collected at each node from August 2024 to November 2025, can be seen in Figure 2. Proportion of positive individuals (bird-level prevalence) per week over the total project period, all nodes combined, show two peaks in 2025, one in August and one in September (Figure 3).

FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In total, 20,834 samples (negative samples in blue; samples positive for avian influenza virus in orange) have been collected at seven nodes between August 2024 and November 2025, yielding 1,571 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 26 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

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Figure 3 Weekly bird-level prevalence of avian influenza virus in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Weekly prevalence of individuals positive for avian influenza virus from all nodes combined between August 2024 and November 2025. The figure only includes bird samples (excluding mussels). The number of individuals (here: any individual bird sampled on a given day) are included at the top of the figure.

2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on the 5th of November (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17533839>), and as of 15th November 2025, no new H5 avian influenza sequences have been generated.

The latest and previous Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

However, there have been a number of non-H5 avian influenza sequences generated from samples collected in Georgia (Node 4 Eastern Black Sea; N=2) and Sweden (Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea; N=84) since the last report. The two sequences from Georgia were of the H1N1 and H9N2 subtypes. From Sweden, 23 genome sequences from samples containing only one subtype have been generated and these included: 1xH2N7, 6xH3N8, 5xH4N6, 6xH6N2, 1xH10N2, 1xH12N5, 1xH12N6, 1xH12N8, and 1xH16N3. In addition, there were 13 samples that were found to contain sequences from multiple subtypes including the following H-types: 2xH2, 9xH3, 3xH4, 4xH6, 2xH8, 1xH11, 7xH12, and N-types: 3xN2, 3xN4, 7xN5, 2xN6, 2xN7, 8xN8.

3. CONCLUSION

With over 1,500 individual birds representing close to 30 species sampled across nine countries during the current period, the coverage of active surveillance of wild birds in and near Europe remains substantial.

Since the beginning of October, multiple outbreaks of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) have been reported across Europe. Although some regional variation in reporting effort exists, the spatiotemporal pattern broadly follows the main migratory routes of waterbirds during autumn. This is the period when large numbers of immunologically naïve juveniles migrate and aggregate at staging and wintering sites, conditions that typically facilitate virus transmission.

Among wild species, Common Cranes in Germany, but also in France and Spain, have been particularly affected. These outbreaks in cranes are notable given the species' high susceptibility and mortality following HPAI infection (Djordjević *et al.* 2024). Cranes are therefore less likely to act as reservoirs or long-distance vectors for the virus, yet their use of shared foraging and roosting areas with Anatidae may contribute to local amplification and interspecies transmission. A decline in crane cases may be expected as mortality progresses and migratory movements continue southward, but the situation warrants continued monitoring.

Since August, two peaks in prevalence have been recorded before the outbreaks in cranes occurred (Figure 3). No cranes were sampled within the project, and positive samples were mainly found in dabbling ducks around the Baltic Sea and in Georgia. Although cranes may use the same habitats as dabbling ducks, a causal connection cannot be demonstrated. The peaks in prevalence most likely reflect the usual autumn increase in low pathogenicity avian influenza (LPAI) virus circulation among dabbling ducks, though elevated early-season prevalence may indicate generally favourable conditions for subsequent virus amplification.

During this period, one Eurasian Teal trapped in Italy tested positive for HPAI H5N1 virus. In addition, a wide variety of LPAI subtypes were detected, including several H1, H3, H4, H6, H8, H12, and H13 viruses, and indications of mixed infections within single samples. Such findings illustrate the high subtype diversity and complex ecology of influenza A viruses in wild waterbirds. However, understanding the dynamics of such mixed infections is complicated, as differences in Ct values are inherently dependent on the viral load at the time of sampling and therefore the infection kinetics of the different viruses. Nevertheless, the repeated detection of mixed infections suggests that co-circulation of multiple subtypes remains a key opportunity for reassortment and genetic diversification within the wild bird reservoir.

The combination of an early prevalence peak, the many LPAI subtypes, and the subsequent emergence of HPAI outbreaks underlines the importance of maintaining intensive surveillance during late summer and autumn. Continued coordination between nodes, timely sharing of genomic data, and integration of ecological and virological information will strengthen the capacity to detect early signals of viral change and to support risk assessment.

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Node 4: Centre of Wildlife Disease Ecology (CWDE), Ilia State University; State Laboratory of Agriculture of Georgia

Node 6: Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES) (Austria); Verein für die Betreuung des Naturschutzgebietes Rheindelta (Naturschutzverein Rheindelta) (Austria); Friedrich-Loeffler-Institute (FLI) (Germany); Max-Planck-Institut für Verhaltensbiologie (MPI) (Germany); National Reference Centre for Poultry and Rabbit Diseases (NRGK) (Switzerland); Swiss Institute for Virology and Immunology (IVI) (Switzerland)

Node 7: Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale delle Venezie; Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale (ISPRA)

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